

MENARA Working Documents

No. 3, April 2019

THE MENARA FACT-FINDING MISSIONS: MAIN RESULTS

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 693244

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INTRODUCTION

This report aims to provide an analysis of the interviews conducted in the scope of the MENARA Fact-Finding Missions. Each respondent was asked three questions: (1) Which traditional or new actors will shape the future of the Middle East and North Africa? Why? (2) In your opinion, what are the three main risks and the three main opportunities facing the MENA region? (3) Do you envisage a more or less active European Union in the MENA region in the years to come? And what would you expect from it? This report was produced to make quantifiable and analysable the responses given to these three open-ended questions.

The following section introduces the sample data. Then, each question is examined in a separate section. For question 1, different actors mentioned by the respondents as influential in the MENA region are categorized (local, regional, and global; state, non-state, and phenomena; and armed and other types of non-state actors) and cross-referenced with the profiles of the respondents. The tables and figures in this section, which contain exact numbers as well as percentages, show the distribution of the mentioned actors by level and type for each subgroup of our sample.

For question 2, we have written down and categorized each risk and opportunity mentioned by the respondents. As with the first question, we cross-referenced the mentioned risks and opportunities separately with the other variables and displayed them in figures (exact number of mentions and percentages within sub-groups). Additionally, in this section, we assigned a level of hope to each interviewee based on the number of risks and opportunities they mentioned. Those who mentioned more opportunities were given higher numbers – from 0 (only risks mentioned) to 4 (only opportunities mentioned). The figures in this part show the average levels of hope for each subgroup of our sample.

For question 3, we codified the level of EU activity in the MENA region envisaged by respondents from 1 (less active) to 3 (more active). We then calculated and presented the average levels of EU activity expected by each subgroup in figures. Using a free online service we have produced a word cloud showing the keywords mentioned by respondents with sizes in proportion to their frequencies. This part also includes the main areas of EU activity expected by the respondents together with the frequencies of words associated with each category.

Finally, we provide selected responses to each question at the end of the respective sections. Since the responses are not the respondents' direct words, they are not to be quoted as such. Any part of this report, as well as the dataset Excel file, may be used and further developed in research papers to be delivered as part of the MENARA Project.

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Our sample: There are 269 respondents in the sample. In addition to their responses to the three questions, the dataset contains information on gender, region of origin, age and professional category, and the country where the interview was conducted. The distribution of respondents is as follows:

Gender: Although respondents are not representative of the population, the sample reflects the male-dominated elite class. Nevertheless, the number of female respondents in the sample allows us to make comparisons. This variable enables us to see if there are gender differences in perceptions regarding influential actors, risks and opportunities, and the role of and expectations of the EU.

Table 1 | Gender distribution of the sample

Gender	Frequency	% of total
Female	53	19.7
Male	191	71.0
Missing	25	9.3
Total	269	100

Source: MENARA fact-finding missions. Created by CIDOB.

Country: The country data shown in Figure 1 represents the location of the interviews as well as which countries are included in a given sub-region (e.g. Iraq, Lebanon, Syria and Israel are categorized as the Levant). Throughout the report, only the sub-regions will be presented in tables and figures. This variable will help us identify the effect of geography on perceptions. We have grouped them into sub-regions when relevant.

Figure 1 | Country distribution of the sample

Figure 2 | Map of the sample distribution by country

Region of origin: This indicates whether a respondent is originally from the MENA or other regions (non-MENA). This variable will help us understand differences, if any exist, between people from the region and external observers (e.g. diplomats).

Figure 3 | Regional distribution of the sample

Age group: Despite not representing the predominantly young demography of the region, the sample is representative of the age group of the decision-makers both inside and outside the region. Nevertheless, it contains a significant number of young people whose data will provide us with the generational gaps and differences in perceptions and expectations, if any exist (Figure 4).

Figure 4 | Age distribution of the sample

Professional category: Figure 5 indicates the professional categories of the respondents. This variable will provide insights into any differences between people from various fields such as public officials, the private sector, members of civil society, intellectuals, opinion makers, and activists.

Figure 5 | Categorical distribution of the sample

QUESTION 1: “WHICH TRADITIONAL OR NEW ACTORS WILL SHAPE THE FUTURE OF THE MIDDLE EAST AND NORTH AFRICA? WHY?”

This question, like the other two, was open-ended. The respondents provided a plethora of actors they viewed as significant in the future of the MENA region. The most extensive list provided contained as many as 11 actors while most respondents mentioned three or four. We then categorized the mentioned actors by type: state and non-state actors, and phenomena (e.g. migration), and by their level: local, regional, and global. We also differentiated armed non-state actors from other non-state actors.

State actors include states, governments, government bodies such as the monarchy, the army, and the parliament as well as intergovernmental and supranational organizations such as the EU and the GCC. Non-state actors are those that are not officially a part of a state such as civil society organizations, armed non-state actors, political parties, and social movements. Although the question asked about actors, some of the respondents cited factors such as water, terrorism, religion, sectarianism and so on as the shapers of the future of the region. We categorized those answers as phenomena.

As for the local actors, we included those operating within a country’s boundaries. Most of the non-state actors fall into this category except for those that operate in and influence more than one country’s politics and economy such as transnational civil society organizations or terrorist organizations fighting in more than one country. Regional actors, on the other hand, include the states and supranational institutions located in the region as well as non-state actors that are effective in more than one of the region’s countries. Finally, global actors are the international powers outside the region such as the USA, the UN, the EU, and Russia.

Different respondents listed different numbers of total actors, giving us 877 mentions of individual actors in our database. After categorizing the actors, we used pivot tables in MS Excel 2010 to identify the ten actors respondents mentioned most. All are state actors. This is why we have also included in our analysis “women”, “youth”, “CSOs”, and “armed non-state actors (all organizations and groups combined)”, even though they did not make the top ten list.

Typology of actors: As Figure 6 indicates, state actors were far more frequently cited as being influential in the MENA region than non-state actors were. This reflects a state-centric perception of the existing regional order

Figure 6 | Types of actors mentioned

Regional, global or local actors: according to this sample the three kinds of actors play a role but respondents tend to attribute a larger influence to regional ones.

Figure 7 | Frequency distribution of levels of actors mentioned

Type of non-state actor: Contrary to the widespread media coverage of armed non-state actors (NSAs), respondents view other types of NSAs as far more influential.

Figure 8 | Frequencies of sub-categories of non-state actors vs. state actors

The top ten single actors and the four big ones: As reflected in Figure 9, the ten actors mentioned most frequently by the respondents as influential actors in the region are all state actors. Within those ten, there is a big gap between the top four – the USA, Saudi Arabia, Iran and Russia – and the fifth actor, Turkey. As that top four includes two global actors, the US and Russia, and two regional actors, Saudi Arabia and Iran, it may suggest some sort of multi-bipolarity: US vs Russia at global level; Saudi Arabia vs Iran at regional.

Figure 9 | Frequency of most-frequently mentioned actors

WHO MENTIONED WHAT?

Location of interviews and actor types: As Figure 10 shows, the non-state actor percentages are higher in the Sahel, Maghreb and Levant countries, while they were lowest in Turkey and Gulf countries.

Figure 10 | Frequency and percentage distribution of types of actors mentioned in a given country or sub-region

Location of interviews and actor levels: As seen in Figure 11, in interviews conducted in Turkey and Iran global actors were mentioned more than regional and local ones, while in Egypt and Gulf countries regional actors were more prevalent. Local actors, on the other hand, were more frequently mentioned in Maghreb countries while being almost absent in the Gulf.

Figure 11 | Frequency and percentage distribution of levels of actors mentioned in a given country or sub-region

Location of interviews and armed non-state actors: Figure 12 shows that armed non-state actors were mentioned more than other NSAs in the Sahel and were absent from interviews made in Turkey and Egypt and almost absent in the Gulf. Other NSAs, on the other hand, were mentioned in Maghreb and Levant countries and Egypt more than armed NSAs.

Figure 12 | Frequency and percentage distribution of armed NSAs and other NSAs within all actors mentioned in a given country or sub-region

TOP TEN MOST FREQUENTLY MENTIONED ACTORS AND CSOs, WOMEN AND YOUNG PEOPLE

This section introduces the region, country, professional category, age and gender data of the respondents in terms of their mentioning of the top ten most frequently mentioned actors as well as those that mentioned CSOs, women and young people as influential actors in the MENA region. In other words, it provides, for each subgroup of the said variables, the distribution of the mentioned actors in both exact figures and percentages.

Region of origin and actors: As Figure 13 indicates, young people are not mentioned by respondents from outside the MENA region. The frequency percentage of Israel being mentioned by MENA respondents is almost double that of those outside the MENA. Egypt's percentage in the MENA is higher than that in the non-MENA. Finally, China has much less prevalence among respondents from the MENA than among those who are not.

Figure 13 | Frequency and percentage distribution of the top ten most commonly mentioned actors and CSOs, women, and youth by region

Actors	MENA	Non-MENA	Total
Algeria	16	6	22
China	13	23	36
CSOs	11	7	18
Egypt	19	5	24
EU	21	12	33
Iran	43	31	74
Israel	13	14	27
KSA	50	28	78
Russia	45	27	72
Turkey	25	13	38
USA	51	31	82
Women	3	0	3
Youth	15	0	15
Total	325	197	522

Source: MENARA fact-finding missions. Created by CIDOB.

Figure 14 | Frequency and percentage distribution of the top ten most frequently mentioned actors and CSOs, women, and youth by the country the interview was done

Location of interviews and actors: As seen in Figure 14, in the interviews conducted in Turkey the US and Russia are almost equally prevalent, followed by Saudi Arabia and Iran. Another interesting finding from those interviews is that the EU and Turkey were mentioned the least. Algeria was mentioned only in interviews made in the Maghreb and Sahel countries where the prevalence of the US, Saudi Arabia, Iran and Russia, the top four in our list, is much lower than in other countries.

Instead, the EU's percentage is significantly higher in these countries than in others. China is absent from interviews made in Egypt, the Sahel and Turkey and almost absent in the Levant. Iran, on the other hand, is much less prevalent in the Maghreb and non-existent in the Sahel.

Israel's percentages were similar in the interviews conducted in Egypt, the Gulf, the Levant and in outside the MENA region while it was never mentioned in Iran, the Maghreb, Sahel or Turkey. Saudi Arabia, on the other hand, does appear in the Sahel and is less prevalent in the Maghreb and Turkey than in other countries. CSOs were not mentioned in the Gulf, Iran or Turkey while they were more prevalent in Sahel and Maghreb countries than other locations. The young were also absent from interviews from external, Gulf and Sahel countries and Turkey while they were around 10 per cent in Maghreb and Levant countries. Finally, women were mentioned as influential actors in the MENA region only in the Levant and Iran.

Figure 15 | Frequency and percentage distribution of the top ten most commonly mentioned actors and CSOs, women, and youth by the professional category of the respondents

Professional category and actors: As Figure 15 shows, Iran and Russia are less prevalent among the respondents from the private sector than from the other two categories. However, the opposite is true for Turkey. Finally, young people are cited with much less prevalence by politicians and officials than the other categories.

Age group and actors: As indicated in Figure 16, China was never mentioned by those over 65 and Saudi Arabia was less prevalent. Russia’s percentage was lower among 35–65 year olds, while Turkey was also absent among those over 65 and less prevalent among 35–65 year olds.

Figure 16 | Frequency and percentage distribution of the top ten most frequently mentioned actors and CSOs, women, and youth by the age group of the respondents

Actors	18-35 y	35-65 y	Over 65 y	Total
Algeria	2	18	2	22
China	8	28	0	36
CSOs	5	12	1	18
Egypt	7	16	1	24
EU	8	23	2	33
Iran	29	43	2	74
Israel	10	16	1	27
KSA	25	51	2	78
Russia	30	38	4	72
Turkey	19	19	0	38
USA	26	51	5	82
Women	1	3	0	4
Youth	5	12	1	18
Total	175	330	21	526

Gender and actors: As seen in Figure 17, CSOs, the youth and women were more prevalent among female respondents while Israel was more frequently mentioned by male respondents.

Figure 17 | Frequency and percentage distribution of the top ten most frequently mentioned actors and CSOs, women, and youth by the gender of the respondents

INSIGHTS FROM THE FACT-FINDING MISSIONS

In an interview in Italy, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is an external observer, said: “Local actors, not external ones [are influential]. There is a civil war going on in the MENA, the future of the MENA will depend on its outcome (e.g. sectarian rivalry, Shia–Sunni and intra-Sunni competitors such as Salafis vs MbS, technocratic patrimonial lines like in Saudi Arabia). External actors can only play a role to the extent that local actors call them in and they are willing to be drawn in (e.g. Syria). No new actors economically. People deluded about stability and safety of Saudi Arabia.”

In an interview conducted in the US, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is of MENA origin, mentioned that: “The actors have been pretty much the same for the last 20–30 years, with a shift in weights. All new actors are tools in the hands of regional and global powers (Saudi Arabia, Iran, United States, Russia, Israel).”

In an interview conducted in the US, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is an external observer, said that: “Current dynamics put Turkey, Saudi Arabia, Iran, the US and Russia in the spotlight. Personal level: Mohammed bin Salman, President Erdoğan. Main issue: the evolving foreign policy orientation of Turkey and reforms in Saudi Arabia. If MbS fails it could change a lot of things in the region.”

In an interview conducted in Hungary, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is an external observer, thinks that: “Non-state actors and outside powers will shape this future to a great extent, through using religious, ethnic and tribal identities, economic influence, or even organized crime networks and PMCs (private military companies).”

In an interview conducted in Tunisia, a pro-government politician of MENA origin, argued that: “The distinction between ‘traditional’ and ‘new actors’ needs to be problematized, as we might wonder what a “traditional actor” is. The most important actors who will define the future of the MENA are those that are transnational, be they political forces or armed groups, civil society organizations or cultural groups.”

In an interview conducted in the UK, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is of MENA origin, said: “There has been no significant change in the political actors in the Middle East, as the old players are still running the political game. The Gulf regimes stand side by side with the United States and the United Kingdom at the expense of national movements demanding democratic change. There were opportunities for the development of civil society. But 2011 ended them. The growing role of transnational organizations and the rise of the so-called resistance axis is a game changer for Middle East policy.”

In an interview conducted in Lebanon, an official in an IGO, who is of MENA origin, said: “Iran, Saudi Arabia and Turkey [as influential actors]. The affairs of the Middle East are being controlled by the two poles: Iran and Saudi Arabia. The leaders and the people alike in the region are mainly concerned with the future of Iran–Saudi Arabia relations, since the two powers have been remotely controlling the future of peace and war in the region, as is evident in: (a) The open and internationalized wars in Syria and Yemen, and the ongoing and re-emerging issues in Bahrain and Iraq; and (b) the rise of ISIS and its utilization in the face of rising Iranian influence.”

In an interview conducted in Qatar, a respondent working in the private sector, who is of MENA origin, thinks that: “The USA lost its hegemony. Since then nobody leads, every state is for itself. Due to the lack of trust and cooperation, no blocs emerge. Power is diffused among all states.”

In an interview conducted in Qatar, a pro-government politician of MENA origin stated: “The USA is getting more and more passive, the UK is caught up with Brexit, France is getting more active, especially in the Maghreb and the Mashreq. Germany is more visible in economic terms. The lack of unity among Arab states make it easier for Iran, Turkey, Russia and China to be more active.”

In an interview conducted in Qatar, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is of MENA origin, thinks that: “There are no dominant players any more. Absence of hegemony. Actor-pluralism, many actors compete with each other, which makes political outcomes unforeseeable. The USA is less and less influential since the Obama administration. Today’s American foreign policy doesn’t have a clear strategy or priorities. This tendency makes other states more conservative in foreign policy.”

In an interview conducted in Qatar, an official in the public administration, who is an external observer, mentioned that: “The perception of the USA as the hegemon is changing. Washington is not able to handle the crises of the region by itself. This creates an opportunity for others to come in; nonetheless others are not able to achieve anything by themselves either. Russian influence is growing; Israel is not negligible.”

In an interview conducted in China, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is an external observer, said: “Not sure what will happen with China. We have never been a critical actor in the region. Now, the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) demonstrates we are interested but still the traditional superpowers (mainly the US) are the ones who will remain critical in shaping the region’s future.”

In an interview conducted in the UK, an official in the public administration, who is an external observer, explained that: “In the short term Russia is reinforcing security in some parts of the MENA according to its interests but in the long terms it is actually undermining the stability and development of the region and does not seem to have a clear plan. The same goes for the Gulf countries. Countries such as Saudi Arabia and Qatar are today less and less inclined to use proxies to influence the MENA countries’ future and prefer to do it themselves.”

In an interview conducted in the UK, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is an external observer, raised the point that: “The increased role of the Gulf states makes the MENA region more dynamic but also increasingly unequal. It creates the impression that the real problems are geopolitics-driven while in reality there are more important and structural debates that are going on in some parts of the region that are bound to have an impact on it, i.e., technology, women’s issues, automated work. When it comes to the relationship between the regional players (particularly the Gulf ones) and the United States, the former tend to have more autonomy than the latter. They are asking the United States to do more than it is willing to do.”

In an interview conducted in Belgium, an official in an IGO, who is an external observer, said: “The external actors’ role is not the determining one for the future of the region. The regional players are those calling the shots, in particular Iran and Saudi Arabia. However, the United States, Russia and China are important actors too and their presence is felt across the MENA. The United States is not so disengaged from the region that it cannot do that. At the same time, it is developing an increasingly transactional and business-oriented attitude vis-à-vis the countries in the region, which is in line with their cooperation approaches. Russia is a tactical actor towards the MENA, while the only strategic actor is China.”

In an interview conducted in Belgium, an official in an IGO, who is an external observer, argued that: “In terms of specific actors, the United States remains predominant by being present or by being absent. The case of the Syrian conflict is illustrative in this respect as the US is now back after a gap that coincided with the final part of Obama’s presidency and the beginning of Trump’s. This may change the equation, particularly when it comes to coordination or cooperation with Russia. Concerning the regional actors, both Iran and Saudi Arabia will continue to have an influence on the region despite a number of internal (and of course bilateral) problems. Both countries may be black holes or driving forces depending on how internal dynamics evolve.”

In an interview conducted in Belgium, an official in an IGO, who is an external observer, explained: “There has undoubtedly been a change of actors in the MENA. While in the past the most important used to be Egypt, Syria and Iraq, now they are all faced by a number of challenges that diminish their capacity to act as autonomous and influential players in the MENA region. Take the case of Egypt. It is nowadays wedded to Saudi Arabia by a marriage of ideology and of interest. Therefore, it does not have the capacity to develop an autonomous foreign policy. The relatively new heavyweights on the regional scene are those that used to be payers at best and now are players: Saudi Arabia, the UAE and Qatar. They have used money diplomacy (money in Africa and contract diplomacy in Europe) to achieve this status. Is it sustainable for them? For Saudi Arabia it is not, due to a number of factors including demographic pressure, a hard-dying development model and leadership vagaries. For example, it is already clear that Saudi Arabia has lost everything in Syria after investing a lot. Turning to Iran, it is more strategic and less irrational than the Arab Gulf players.”

QUESTION 2: “IN YOUR OPINION, WHAT ARE THE THREE MAIN RISKS AND THE THREE MAIN OPPORTUNITIES FACING THE MENA REGION?”

For this question we have written down the risks and opportunities mentioned by the respondents separately. Similar to what we did with the actors, we increased our sample size from 269 to 825 for risks and to 463 for opportunities. We then categorized risks and opportunities into economic, environmental, political, security and geopolitics, and societal as can be seen in Tables 9 and 14. Additionally, for opportunities, we created a “no opportunities” category for the respondents who indicated that they do not see any opportunities for the region. We then analysed the risks and opportunities in separate sections using pivot tables.

For risks and opportunities, this section provides tables and figures showing the frequencies and percentages of each risk and opportunity by type, the top lists that were mentioned ten times or more, and the gender, region of origin, age group and professional category of the respondents as well as the location of interviews mentioning each risk and opportunity type. As it is the most significant variable in terms of the risk and opportunity perceptions of respondents, we also included the five most frequently mentioned risks and opportunities in each location.

Risks: Security and geopolitics-related risks were mentioned more than all other types combined, as shown in Figure 18. The Figure also indicates the 24 risks that were mentioned ten times or more, with conflicts, terrorism, authoritarianism, extremism, and political instability at the top.

Figure 18 | Risks types and their frequency (risks mentioned ten times or more)

Risks and their types: Table 2 shows the distribution of risks and how they have been categorized. Risk types are shown in bold above their contents. The numbers next to the risks indicate their frequency in interviews.

Table 2 | Frequency and type of risks

Economic		Security and geopolitics				Societal	
economic situation	38	conflicts	74	GCC crisis	5	migration	21
poverty	21	terrorism	55	USA	5	inequalities	10
unemployment	19	extremism	46	Hezbollah	4	frustration	8
lack of skills	17	fragmentation	35	maritime insecurity	4	demographics	7
rentierism	12	state failure	27	Saudi Arabia	4	generational gap	7
oil prices	5	Iran	17	Turkey	3	intolerance	7
energy	4	Iran-Saudi rivalry	16	Algeria	2	social backwardness	6
technology	4	militias	14	China	2	social exclusion	3
sanctions	3	sectarianism	14	Egypt	2	social instability	2
underdevelopment	3	foreign intervention	13	France	2	Anti-Semitism	1
lack of investment	2	Arab-Israeli conflict	10	Syria	2	materialism	1
Political		Libya	9	Afghanistan	1	urbanization	1
authoritarianism	48	nuclearization	9	cyber-security	1	Youth	1
political instability	46	insecurity	8	globalization	1	Environmental	
corruption	21	Superpower rivalry	8	humanitarian crises	1	environment	21
bad governance	20	Russia	7	Israel	1	natural resources	10
disinformation	6	weapons	7	Israel-Iran rivalry	1	water	9
isolationism	1	crimes	6	Sahara	1		
lack of leadership	1	lack of foreign support	6	Sahel	1		
nationalism	1	militarization	6	Sub-Saharan Africa	1		
political exclusion	1	West	6				

WHO MENTIONED WHAT?

This section provides the distribution of risk types by respondents' gender, the country where the interview was conducted, the region of origin, the age group, and the professional category of the respondents.

Gender: As Figure 19 indicates, gender is not a significant factor for perceived risk types for the MENA region.

Figure 19 | Frequency and percentage distributions of risk types by gender

Location: As seen in Figure 20, there are significant variations in risk-type perception between the locations where interviews were held. Economic risks were mentioned more frequently in interviews in Turkey and the Gulf and less in external and Levant countries. The prevalence of economic concerns in the Gulf might be due to rentierism, while in Turkey it may be because of the recent decline in the Turkish economy.

Environmental concerns were more prevalent in interviews done in Iran but absent in the Sahel and Turkey. The increasing air and water pollution in Iran might be behind such prevalence.

Political risks were mentioned more in the Levant and Egypt and less in the Gulf and Sahel. The distribution of security and geopolitics risks is the highest in the Sahel, followed by the Maghreb, Gulf and external countries. State failure, rise of armed non-state actors and conflicts in that area may be the reasons security and geopolitical concerns have a larger distribution in the Sahel.

Finally, societal concerns were more prevalent in the Levant than in other locations with similar distributions in this regard. Sectarian conflicts, demographic changes, and widespread ethno-sectarian discrimination may be contributing to a larger share of societal concerns in the Levant by comparison with other locations.

Figure 20 | Frequency and percentage distributions of risk types by location of the interview

Table 3 shows the top risks mentioned in each specific location. The locations are indicated in bold and the figure next to each risk is the number of mentions by respondents in the respective country or sub-region. This table is meant to give an understanding of the common risks as well as particularities. It indicates that although there are shared concerns in the whole MENA region, the perceived priority of threats is subject to variation.

Among the commonalities are conflicts, authoritarianism and extremism. The peculiarities, on the other hand, are Iran in external countries, corruption in the Levant, state failure in the Sahel, rentierism in the Gulf, and sanctions in Iran.

Table 3 | Top risks mentioned most frequently in interviews from different locations

Egypt		External		Levant		Sahel	
Authoritarianism	7	Conflicts	18	Authoritarianism	13	migration	21
Conflicts	6	Political instability	18	Extremism	13	inequalities	10
Economic situation	6	Terrorism	15	Corruption	9	frustration	8
Terrorism	5	Authoritarianism	14	Conflicts	8	demographics	7
Extremism	4	Environment	10	Fragmentation	7	generational gap	7
Fragmentation	4	Iran	10	Terrorism	7	intolerance	7
Militarization	4						
Gulf		Iran		Maghreb		Turkey	
Conflicts	8	Conflicts	8	Conflicts	17	Conflicts	5
Rentierism	7	Environment	5	Terrorism	13	Fragmentation	4
Economic situation	5	Extremism	3	Authoritarianism	11	Political instability	4
Iran-Saudi rivalry	5	Political instability	3	Economic situation	11	Authoritarianism	3
Political instability	5	Sanctions	3	Extremism	11	Economic situation	3

Region of origin: As indicated in Figure 21, there are only slight variations among respondents from the MENA and external observers with regards to their perceptions of risks. Security and geopolitics-related risks were mentioned slightly more by external observers while the distribution of political risks is somewhat higher among respondents from the MENA region.

Figure 21 | Frequency and percentage distributions of risk types by region of origin of the respondents

Age group: As indicated in Figure 22, environmental concerns were less prevalent among the 35–65 age group than the other two groups, while the same was the case among those over 65 with regards to societal risks.

Figure 22 | Frequency and percentage distributions of risk types by age group

Professional category: As shown in Figure 23, the perception of economic risks among respondents from the private sector is higher than in the other two categories, while those of environmental, political, and security and geopolitics risks are lower.

Figure 23 | Frequency and percentage distributions of risk types by professional category

As indicated in Table 4, conflicts and political instability are among the top five risks mentioned by all professional categories. The economic situation, Iran–Saudi rivalry, lack of skills and rentierism, on the other hand, appear only among the top five risks mentioned by those working in the private sector while the same list does not contain authoritarianism and terrorism, which appear the other two lists. Extremism is peculiar to the list of CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, while state failure only appears in the politicians and officials list.

Table 4 | Top risks mentioned by professional category

CSO, intellectuals and opinion-makers, activists		Private sector		Politicians and officials	
Conflicts	32	Conflicts	7	Terrorism	35
Extremism	26	Economic situation	6	Conflicts	34
Authoritarianism	22	Iran-Saudi rivalry	4	Authoritarianism	25
Political instability	19	Fragmentation	3	Political instability	24
Fragmentation	18	Lack of skills	3	State failure	22
Terrorism	18	Political instability	3		
		Rentierism	3		

OPPORTUNITIES

Table 5 shows the frequencies of opportunities and opportunity types mentioned by respondents.

Figure 24 shows the frequency of opportunities mentioned ten times or more. The list contains 18 items with youth, dialogue and peace at the top. The fourth most frequently given answer is “there are no opportunities”, which shows the low levels of hope regarding the future of the MENA region. As shown in the Figure, opportunities related to society and the economy were mentioned the most.

Table 5 | Frequencies and types of opportunities

Economic		Political		Societal	
Foreign investment	17	Democracy	15	Youth	38
Investment	17	Regional political cooperation	13	Dialogue	26
Development	16	Political activism	10	Social change	15
Economic reform	9	Political change	10	Education	14
Trade	9	Sense of urgency	10	Demographics	11
Infrastructure	8	Freedoms	9	Women	10
Energy	7	Leadership	7	Civil society	8
Innovation	7	Political reform	7	Culture	7
EU economic support	6	Cooperation	5	ITCs	7
Industry	5	Digital activism	4	Citizenship	3
Job creation	5	EU political engagement	4	Religion	2
Gulf	4	Diasporas	2	Hope	1
Tourism	4	Security and geopolitics		Resilience	1
Economic diversification	3	Peace	21	Social activism	1
Post-oil	3	Foreign support	14	Environmental	
Reconstruction	3	Post-ISIS	7	Natural resources	12
Entrepreneurship	1	Strategic location	5	Renewable energy	9
Regional economic cooperation	1	Counterterrorism	4	Environmental reform	3
Transportation	1	Security reform	2	No opportunities	20
				General total	463

Figure 24 | Distribution of opportunity types

WHO MENTIONED WHAT?

This section provides the distribution of opportunity types by respondents' gender, the country where the interview was conducted, the region of origin, the age group, and the professional category of the respondents.

Gender: As seen in Figure 25, the distribution of opportunity types mentioned by males and females shows only slight variation.

Figure 25 | Frequency and percentage distributions of opportunity types by gender

Location: As indicated in Figure 26, economic opportunities have the highest prevalence among interviews conducted in the Gulf while being absent in the Sahel altogether. The distribution of economic opportunities is also lower in interviews from Turkey, Egypt and the Maghreb. Environmental opportunities have the highest percentage in Turkey and are not mentioned in Egypt, Iran or the Sahel at all. The response “there are no opportunities” has the highest distribution in the Sahel and Egypt. While political opportunities are more prevalent in interviews from external, Gulf and Maghreb countries, they are absent in those in the Sahel and Turkey. Security and geopolitics-related opportunities have higher distributions in the Levant and Turkey but are absent in the Sahel and lower in Egypt. Societal opportunities are more prevalent in Sahel and less in external and Gulf countries. The main outlier in this regard is the Sahel, as it contains responses with societal opportunities only (4). The remaining are either missing, meaning that the

respondent has not mentioned any opportunities, or “there are no opportunities”.

Figure 26 | Frequency and percentage distributions of opportunity types by location of interviews

Table 6 shows the top five opportunities mentioned in each specific location. The locations are indicated in bold and the number next to each opportunity represents the total number of mentions by respondents in the respective country or sub-region. This table is meant to give an understanding of the common opportunities as well as particularities. It indicates that although there are commonly perceived opportunities in the whole MENA region, the perceived priority of such opportunities is subject to variation.

Among the commonalities, despite the exceptions, are youth, peace, and “no opportunities”. The peculiarities, on the other hand, are sense of urgency in Egypt, regional political cooperation in external, women in Iran, counter-terrorism in Maghreb, economic diversification in the Gulf, post-ISIS in Levant, and natural resources in Turkey.

Table 6 | Top opportunities mentioned most frequently in interviews from different locations

Egypt		External		Iran		Maghreb	
No opportunities	7	Regional political cooperation	9	Youth	7	Youth	15
Youth	3	Dialogue	5	Women	5	Dialogue	7
Civil society	2	No opportunities	5	Foreign investment	4	Democracy	6
Demographics	2	Peace	5	Investment	3	Political activism	5
Economic reform	2	Political activism	5	Peace	3	Counterterrorism	4
Sense of urgency	2	Youth	5			Foreign support	4
Turkey		Gulf		Levant		Sahel	
Natural resources	4	Investment	7	Dialogue	9	No opportunities	2
Demographics	2	Peace	4	Development	6	Youth	2
Civil society	1	Dialogue	3	Foreign investment	6	Hope	1
Education	1	Economic diversification	3	Peace	6	Social change	1
Energy	1	Education	3	Democracy	5		
No opportunities	1	Freedoms	3	Post-ISIS	5		
Peace	1	Political reform	3	Social change	5		
Strategic location	1						
Trade	1						
Youth	1						

Region: As seen in Figure 27, the prevalence of economic opportunities is higher among external observers, while that of societal ones is higher among respondents from the MENA region. In other opportunity types, the distributions of both groups are similar.

Figure 27 | Frequency and percentage distributions of opportunity types by region of origin of respondents

Frequency of respondents	Opportunity types	MENA	Non-MENA	Total
	Economic	76	43	126
Environmental	17	7	24	
No opportunities	14	6	20	
Political	63	28	96	
Security & Geopolitics	39	13	53	
Societal	108	32	144	
Total	317	129	463	

Age group: Figure 28 indicates that the distributions of opportunity types are only slightly different between the respondents from age groups 18–35 and 35–65, while among those over 65 economic opportunities are more prevalent and political opportunities are less.

Figure 28 | Frequency and percentage distributions of opportunity types by age group of respondents

Opportunity types	18-35 y	35-65 y	Over 65 y	Total
Economic	35	85	6	126
Environmental	9	14	1	24
No opportunities	5	14	1	20
Political	29	66	1	96
Security and Geopolitics	18	33	2	53
Societal	42	97	5	144
Total	138	309	16	463

Professional category: As Figure 29 shows, the prevalence of economic opportunities is higher among the private sector and lower among the group CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers. Environmental opportunities are less prevalent among politicians and officials while the respondents from the private sector did not mention “no opportunities”. Compared to the other two groups, CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, and activists has a higher distribution of political, security and geopolitics-related, and societal opportunities.

Figure 29 | Frequency and percentage distributions of opportunity types by professional category of respondents

Top opportunities by professional category: As Table 5 shows, youth and dialogue appear in all three lists. Peace, democracy, foreign support and women are particular to the list of CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, and activists. Investment, counterterrorism, the Gulf, and renewable energy are seen only in the top five list for the private sector. Finally, “no opportunities” and development appear only in the politicians and officials list.

Table 5 | Top opportunities mentioned by professional categories

CSO, intellectuals and opinion-makers, activists		Private sector		Politicians and officials	
Youth	26	Foreign investment	4	No opportunities	16
Peace	16	Investment	4	Dialogue	11
Dialogue	12	Youth	4	Foreign investment	11
Democracy	9	Counterterrorism	3	Development	9
Foreign support	8	Dialogue	3	Youth	8
Natural resources	8	Gulf	3		
Women	8	Renewable energy	3		

HOPES AND FEARS

This section provides the level of hope observed among the participants about the future of the MENA region. We codified the responses that either mention that “there are no opportunity” or list risks without mentioning opportunities as “0”. If the number of risks provided is higher than that of opportunities, the code is “1”, while “2” means that the respondent listed equal numbers of risks and opportunities. The responses containing a higher number of opportunities than risks were given “3” while those mentioning only opportunities but no risks were coded as “4”. The average level of hope in our sample is 1.29, closer to pessimism but still containing elements of hope. The following tables and figures show the average level of hope among subgroups of responses based on the gender, region of origin, age group and professional category of respondents as well as the country where the interview was conducted.

Gender and average level of hope: As Figure 30 indicates, the level of hope among female respondents was above the general average and lower among males.

Figure 30 | Gender and average level of hope

Location of interview and average level of hope: As can be seen in Figure 31, the level of hope was highest in interviews conducted in Iran and the Gulf while it was lowest in Egypt and the Sahel.

Figure 31 | Location of interview and average level of hope

Region of origin and average level of hope: Figure 32 shows that the levels of hope among those of MENA origin and external observers were close to the general average, while being slightly higher among the former and lower among the latter.

Figure 32 | Region of origin and average level of hope

Age group and average level of hope: As seen in Figure 33, the level of hope among those over 65 was lower than the general average while it was slightly higher than the average for the 35–65 age group.

Figure 33 | Age group and average level of hope

Professional category and average level of hope: Figure 34 presents a more hopeful private sector and a less optimistic state and government sector.

Figure 34 | Professional category and average level of hope

INSIGHTS FROM THE FACT-FINDING MISSIONS

In an interview conducted in Kuwait, a respondent working in the private sector who is an external observer listed: “Risks: breakup of GCC or toppling of local governments/emirs/MbS, expat labour from India and other places moving back as there are now more opportunities in their home countries. On the other hand, some Arabs in the US and in London might be more inclined to move (back) to the Gulf in the future. Technology and its levelling of borders and distances may be an opportunity, so are Gulf investments in Africa (they have the natural and human resources, the Gulf the capital). Dependency culture, cradle to grave nanny states and the mentality it breeds is a problem for the Gulf’s competitiveness.”

In an interview conducted in Lebanon, a respondent working in the private sector, who is of MENA origin, mentioned: “Risk: ability of Gulf countries to help Egypt and so on financially is declining, could lead to destabilization. Economics could affect unrest: Tunisia, Iran. Opportunities: Biggest opportunity is alternative energy especially solar, but problem: what shall they do with their stranded hydrocarbon assets. Morocco outlier as they are not tied by these hydrocarbon interests. Could become retirement home of Europe as well. Car industry in Morocco, Chinese are the ones that will succeed in electric cars, they are well ahead of everyone and they are trying to go global.”

In an interview in Egypt, an official in an IGO, who is of MENA origin, said: “In terms of risks I can envisage two things: the tensions that will arise from the restructuring of the regional order and increased repression by the regimes from the region. I cannot think of any meaningful opportunity.”

In an interview held in Egypt an official in an IGO, who is of MENA origin, listed: “Risks: fragmentation [...] as a Libyan citizen this is the first thing that comes to my mind. But I am also afraid of something big, something we cannot even think about, some sort of major catastrophe. The risks are also increasingly concentrated in small heavily populated spaces (Gaza, Cairo). In terms of opportunities, nothing comes to my mind. I guess that we are too frustrated with the results of the Arab Spring.”

In an interview conducted in Turkey, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is of MENA origin, explained that: “As far as the risks concerned, these are the three main ones: (1) the existing forms of state (i.e. monarchies and oligarchies), which are against democratization; (2) the perception of society (i.e. challenges in human rights and women issues); (3) the perception of Western states (their indifference to the region for the sake of individual interests). Opportunities vary from one country to another in MENA. In the Gulf, Qatar, Bahrain and Saudi Arabia take the lead with their energy resources, yet only Qatar distinguishes itself among them with its intellectual capacity.”

In an interview conducted in Tunisia, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is of MENA origin, has the view that: “The lack of democracy is the biggest risk facing the MENA region as it brings with it conflicts and underdevelopment. In terms of opportunities, the presence of so many young people is very promising and should be channelled in the direction of empowerment and participation.”

In an interview conducted in Switzerland, an official in an IGO, who is of MENA origin, argued that: “Repression of freedoms is the main risk. Lack of equality between citizens is also a key risk that is due class differences, corruption of states, and sectarianism. I am not optimistic about any opportunities for the region. Authoritarian regimes still receive support from the EU and the US such as Saudi Arabia and Bahrain. Weapons are still sold to such countries to kill civilians, such as in Yemen.”

In an interview conducted in China, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is an external observer, said: “Not really ISIS, the Palestinian issue, but (1) new forms of terrorism (yet I am not really sure this will actually take shape); (2) nuclear issue/ nuclearizing the MENA region, from Iran to the rest of the Gulf (including Oman and Israel, many of whom are major trade partners of China); (3) break-out of a major conflict in the Gulf affecting the whole region, but even before that the expression of this conflict over maritime issues in the Gulf (affecting China’s commercial relations).”

In an interview conducted in Belgium, an official in an IGO, who is an external observer, mentioned: “Risks: (1) authoritarianism 2.0 following the Arab uprisings. Most governing elites in the MENA have a nationalist approach while their populations are embedded in global dynamics and suffer from the same problems as other people across and beyond the region. (2) Most countries in the region with some exceptions (UAE) are very inward-looking. (3) Existing conflicts will continue and new ones might erupt. Actually, the big direct confrontation between Iran and Saudi Arabia has not happened yet and it could be a disruptive and lengthy one. Furthermore, another potentially disruptive conflict of high intensity is the one between Saudi Arabia and Turkey for the leadership of the Sunni world. (4) The (perceived) US disengagement from the region is very problematic as it is the only actor that has the capacity to solve the conflicts in the region.

Opportunities: in the short term there are no opportunities, or better said, some existing opportunities such as the engagement between Israel and some Sunni countries could develop into risks.”

QUESTION 3: “DO YOU ENVISAGE A MORE OR LESS ACTIVE EUROPEAN UNION IN THE MENA REGION IN THE YEARS TO COME? AND WHAT WOULD YOU EXPECT FROM IT?”

We have coded the level of EU activity in the MENA region in the years to come envisaged by the respondents as “1” for “less active”, “2” for “active”, and “3” for “more active”. Then we calculated the averages of subgroups of our sample in terms of the country where the interview was conducted, the region of origin, age group, professional category, and gender of the respondents

using the subtotal function of MS Excel. Higher numbers indicate higher expectations of the EU playing a significant role, the overall mean being 1.8.

Level of activity envisaged by the location of the interviews: As indicated in Figure 35, the average levels of activity are above the general average in interviews conducted in Iran, the Maghreb and Sahel, while the Gulf and Turkey are at the bottom of the list.

Figure 35 | Average level of activity envisaged as per the location of the interviews

Average level of activity envisaged by region of origin: As Figure 36 shows, the expected average of level of EU activity is higher among the external observers than among respondents of MENA origin.

Figure 36 | Average level of activity envisaged as per region of origin

Average level of activity envisaged by age group: As reflected in Figure 37, those over 65 expect the EU to be far less active in the near future than the other two age groups.

Figure 37 | Average level of activity envisaged as per age group

Average level of activity envisaged by professional category: As indicated in Figure 38, the EU is anticipated to be less active by the respondents from the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, and activists than those in the other two professional categories.

Figure 38 | Average level of activity envisaged as per professional category

Average level of activity envisaged by gender: Figure 39 shows that male respondents are expecting a more active EU than females.

Figure 39 | Average level of activity envisaged as per gender

WHICH TOPICS ARE MENTIONED?

In order to determine the most frequently mentioned words in the answers to Question 3, we have listed the most mentioned concepts. After removing common words unrelated to our topic such as “will”, “does”, “actor”, “think” or those that are more general such as “support(ing)”, we categorized the words in our list in five clusters of topics that are identified as the ones that will either push the EU to be more involved or where the EU could have a greater impact. Those clusters are: (1) economy (which includes development and cooperation efforts); (2) security (which also includes terrorism and the need to cope with crises originating in the neighbourhood); (3) values such as human rights, freedoms, norms, democracy and civil society; (4) politics covering influence, stance, transformation and governance; and (5) migration and refugees.

Respondents who expressed that the EU would not be able to play a significant role mentioned the lack of unified vision in the EU and the existence of internal crises that divert the EU’s attention and resources. Some of these answers can be found in the “Insights from the Fact-Finding Missions” part at the end of this section.

Figure 40 | Clusters of topics with their frequencies in the responses

Other global actors: Some respondents spontaneously mentioned other global actors with whom the EU may cooperate or compete. As shown in Figure 41, those actors are: the US, Russia and China but also some member states- France is the country that is mentioned most, followed by Germany. Interestingly, other Mediterranean states such as Italy and Spain are barely mentioned and the UK is no longer discussed when respondents elaborate on the role of the EU. This could be the result of a perception that the UK is less influential or that the UK is no longer associated with the EU.

Figure 41 | Other global actors and Individual EU members with their frequencies in the responses and main topics related

INSIGHTS FROM THE FACT-FINDING MISSIONS

In an interview conducted in Iran, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is of MENA origin, argues that: “There is less EU involvement in the region since the MENA’s strategic weight for the EU has decreased due to the terrorist threat and refugees.”

In an interview conducted in Iran, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is of MENA origin, thinks that: “There will be more EU involvement because of the threats of terrorism, migration and refugees – the EU should be more involved in development issues and should strengthen indigenous development in countries.”

In an interview conducted in Kuwait, a participant working in public administration, who is of MENA origin, mentioned that: “Europe [is] not that active in the region. Its FTAs and offtake agreements for textiles with Egypt and Tunisia have not really benefitted these countries. Europe does not speak with one voice.”

In an interview conducted in Kuwait, an official at an IGO, who is of MENA origin, articulated that: “Europe has fallen into too many incoherencies. The focus for Europe should be to be in listening mode. Once it has understood the priorities and the constraints, Europe can do a lot in terms of helping the countries and societies from the region to deal with many of challenges from a regional perspective as well as by building stronger institutions (nationally but also regionally).”

In an interview conducted in Kuwait, an official at an IGO, who is of MENA origin, argues that: “The US is disengaging from the region. It is up to the EU to decide if they want to fill this vacuum. Moreover, in the region, Europe is more acceptable than the US.”

In an interview conducted in Turkey, a participant working in public administration, who is of MENA origin, mentioned that: “I don’t think the EU will become a perished actor in the region. With its soft power tools [i.e. infrastructure, civil society, foreign aid commission], the EU continues to demonstrate its influence in the MENA region. What I think is that the EU will remain active as long as it shows its determination to share its economic/social means to the region.”

In an interview conducted in Turkey, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is of MENA origin, thinks that: “The EU is consuming all of its energy in its internal crises, especially with the Brexit process, this has become much clearer. The union has potential to act as a moral soft power; however, there are discrepancies between its actions and values. The union’s internal dynamics should first be settled down if it targets increasing its already low impact in the region.”

In an interview conducted in the US, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is of MENA origin, envisages the EU: “More active, especially from the side of Germany, due to the high number of refugees in Germany. European non-state actors will also rise in the MENA region. Continuation of liberalization policy, especially towards those countries where there are growth opportunities.”

In an interview conducted in the US, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers who is an external observer sees the EU to be: “Less active. EU institutions do not have the necessary consensus among member states and the necessary political will to handle conflicts there. EU and member states will provide technical assistance, arms and humanitarian aid.”

In an interview conducted in Egypt, an official at an IGO, who is of MENA origin, said: “Expects continuations in what is framed as “European complicity” in the ongoing repression in Egypt. EU, France, Germany and Italy are all buying into the short-term security prism of the Sisi government due to fears of refugees and terrorism. Expects more of that in the future.”

In an interview conducted in Morocco, a pro-opposition politician, who is of MENA origin, said that: “Since 2011, the European Union’s role has been increasingly weak. We speak about the EU but the reality is that the countries of the EU act according to their national interests. Furthermore, the EU also acts differently depending on which MENA country they interact with. The EU in Morocco is not the same as the EU in Libya, Syria, Yemen and Egypt. In Morocco, the country that handles the power is France. Finally, the EU’s role is never independent from that of the United States.”

In an interview conducted in Libya, a participant working in the private sector, who is of MENA origin, explained that: “The EU could play a more important role: (1) in the Mediterranean basin; (2) in exerting stronger influence in French-speaking countries; (3) in energy-producing countries, especially in North Africa (Libya, Algeria); (4) in pushing for a rapprochement between the countries of Africa and North Africa.”

In an interview conducted in Libya, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is of MENA origin, mentioned that: “The European Union will have a great deal of activity in the coming stage, especially on the issue of migration, but it will not be effective enough for the following reasons: (1) EU organizations deal with conflict countries, especially in the North African region, through the security angle, but this is not efficient. For example, security is always privileged over human rights when the subject touches on European national security. (2) The division of Europe or the departure of Britain could cause the dispersal or division of Europe’s policies towards the North African region and the Middle East.”

In an interview conducted in Tunisia, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is of MENA origin, thinks that: “Because of the existence of conflicts on its doorstep (Libya, Syria), the EU will always look at the MENA as one of its areas of strategic interest. At the same time, the EU has given up its role as a promoter of top-down change, which is a good thing, but this has not been substituted by anything else.”

In an interview conducted in the UK, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is of MENA origin, said that: “The EU is expected to be more active in supporting democratic transition in future, especially since it will not be subjected to British pressure after Brexit. It is important for the EU to have a clear vision in support of genuine democratic transformation, because such a transformation means greater stability in the region and growth of common interests between the peoples and governments in both regions.”

In an interview conducted in Lebanon, a participant working in public administration, who is of MENA origin, argues that: “The problem with the EU is that it does not have a joint foreign policy. Even France and Germany, who lead the EU bloc, have different policies. I do not expect the EU to do anything in the region. However, we want the EU to play a role in the Middle East because its stance is unbiased to a certain extent compared to the US and Russian stances.”

In an interview conducted in China, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is an external observer, mentioned that: “China believes that in the end the EU will have to/be forced to do more than it is doing now in the Middle East. Who else will take on the responsibilities that everyone is skipping/avoiding? The EU cannot escape the region (due to e.g. immigration flows). The NATO intervention in Libya is an example that shows that they end up doing what it is needed. The EU is a superpower, unlike China.”

In an interview conducted in the UK, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is an external observer, claimed that: “It is a fallacy that the EU is separate from the MENA region/the Mediterranean. This fallacy is the product of nationalisms that are dependent on post-colonial “othering”. The ENP and other EU initiatives after the Arab uprisings have failed due to this fallacy. When we bring the EU into the picture, there is no need to define the MENA region. In terms of policies, throwing money at the region will not be successful, as the recent past demonstrates. The EU should exploit its preference for multilateralism to develop initiatives

of cooperation along the model of the Paris Agreement and the JCPOA.”

In an interview conducted in the UK, a member of the category CSOs, intellectuals and opinion-makers, who is an external observer, thinks that: “The EU and the Member States have much greater stakes than the United States in the future of the MENA. Since 2011, however, they have only addressed the symptoms and not the real causes. The EU is still trapped in its stability-first narrative and due to that it will not be able to provide a meaningful contribution to redress the future of the MENA region in the short to medium term.”

In an interview conducted in Belgium, an official at an IGO, who is an external observer, explained that: “The EU should work to change the perception some governments and people in the MENA have of it, namely that it is in favour of Iran. The added value the EU can bring to the MENA is to work in post-conflict settings, for example in Syria, where it can invest in the material but above all political–institutional reconstruction of war-torn countries. This is where the EU has most leverage and legitimacy to spend in addition to some resources to commit. When it comes to the countries that have not experienced conflicts recently, such as Tunisia, Morocco and Algeria, the EU should work towards preventing them by fostering resilience (specific objectives tailored to each country: for example, restoring a full-speed bilateral EU–Morocco relationship between the end of the mandate of the European Parliament and at the same time agree on partnership priorities with Algeria). The EU should also work within and promote a multilateral setting to address the challenges in the MENA.”

Middle East and North Africa Regional Architecture: Mapping geopolitical shifts, regional order and domestic transformations (MENARA) is a research project that aims to shed light on domestic dynamics and bottom-up perspectives in the Middle East and North Africa amid increasingly volatile and uncertain times.

MENARA maps the driving variables and forces behind these dynamics and poses a single all-encompassing research question: Will the geopolitical future of the region be marked by either centrifugal or centripetal dynamics or a combination of both? In answering this question, the project is articulated around three levels of analysis (domestic, regional and global) and outlines future scenarios for 2025 and 2050. Its final objective is to provide EU Member States policy makers with valuable insights.

MENARA is carried out by a consortium of leading research institutions in the field of international relations, identity and religion politics, history, political sociology, demography, energy, economy, military and environmental studies.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 693244. This project has been funded with support from the European Commission. This publication reflects the views only of the author, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

